

the same level — 50 kg/ha — of P₂O₅ and K₂O. The test variety was ADT3. The azolla covered the plots on the 13th day after introduction and was left without being incorporated till harvest. The wet weight of azolla was recorded 20 days after planting. The values ranged from 0.98 to 1.27 kg/m² (mean of 10 values

was 1.09 kg/m²).

The maximum yield increase by growing azolla as a dual crop without incorporation was 0.2 t/ha; for N application at 25 kg/ha, the yield increase ranged between 0.4 and 0.5 t/ha (see table). It was earlier observed at this station that when azolla at 3 t/ha was introduced as

seed material a week after planting and incorporated on the 13th day — when it has completely covered the area — it gave a yield comparable to that from 25 kg inorganic nitrogen/ha [IRRN 5(3) (Jun 1980): 21]. Therefore, growing azolla without incorporating it did not add any appreciable N input to the crop. ■

Environment and its influence

Effectiveness of supplied nitrogen at the primordial panicle stage on rice plant characteristics and yields

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Ting and associates pointed out in 1959 that formed spikelets and rachis branches of rice usually degenerate during cultivation. Degeneration in the field can be 25.8% for spikelets, 3.8% for the primary branches, and 42.7% for the secondary branches. Matsushima reports that 40-50% of the spikelets degenerate and pointed out in 1957 and 1970 that the reduction division stage, which occurs about 11-13 days before flowering, is most sensitive to degeneration.

We investigated the application of nitrogen to indica rice varieties at the primordial panicle stage to develop improved cultural practices that would increase yields.

The application of nitrogen at the differentiation stage of primary branching increased the number of effective panicles, the number of filled grains per panicle, and the grain yield of the early-season variety Zhen-ZhuZ-Ai more than its application at the formation stage of pistils and stamens, at the formation stage of the pollen mother cell (PMC), or at heading (Table 1). Although nitrogen application at the differentiation stage or at the formation stage of pistils and stamens increases the number of panicles and grains, application at the formation stage of PMC or at the heading stage can increase the number of grains per panicle and grain weight. So, if nitrogen is applied only once, early

application is better.

Field experiments in 1975-1976 with the early-season varieties Nanking-11 and Zhai-Ye-Qing showed that nitrogen applied at the differentiation stage of the first branch primordial (i.e., neck-node initiation) stage and of the primary primordial branch gave 150-225 kg higher grain yield/ha than heavy nitrogen application at the vegetative stage. With the late-season varieties Bao-Tai-Ai and Bao-Gou grain-yield increases

were sometimes 166-787.5 kg/ha.

But nitrogen application only increases yields under the following conditions. 1) Short-statured, nonlodging plants with erect leaves are used. 2) Leaves turn yellowish green at the end of the tillering stage, indicating that carbohydrate metabolism has gained over nitrogen metabolism. The carbohydrates stored in the leaf sheath and stem contribute to panicle growth during the primordial panicle stage, thus filling

Table 1. Effect of nitrogen application at different panicle stages on grain yield using the early-season variety Zhen-Zhu-Ai. Guanezhou, China.

Stage when nitrogen was applied	Effective panicles (no./40 plant hills)	Panicles (no./hill)	Filled grains		1,000-gram wt (g)	Dry grain yield of 40 plant hills (kg)
			No./panicle	%		
Differentiation of primary-branch primordia	494	12.3	118.9	95.5	25.1	0.800
Formation of pistils and stamens	482	12.1	104.6	94.7	25.1	0.775
Formation of pollen mother cell	418	10.4	105.4	93.6	25.8	0.775
Heading	379	9.5	109.8	94.8	25.5	0.700
No treatment	367	9.2	103.5	92.4	25.4	0.700

Table 2. Distribution of ¹⁴C and ¹²P among the different parts of primordial panicle.

Plant parts	³² P (cpm/g dry wt)		¹⁴ C (cpm/g dry wt)	
	Control ^a	Treated ^b	Control ^a	Treated ^b
<i>Differentiation stage</i>				
<i>First bract primordia</i>				
Upper	2,880	2,020	—	—
Middle	2,800	2,890	—	—
Lower	2,560	1,980	—	—
<i>Secondary branch primordia</i>				
Upper	2,040	2,080	—	—
Middle	1,940	2,730	—	—
Lower	1,850	2,720	—	—
<i>Formation stage</i>				
<i>Stamens and pistils</i>				
Upper	3,810	4,450	1,045	1,120
Middle	3,920	5,280	740	1,080
Lower	3,880	4,140	720	1,060

^aNo nitrogen. ^b750 kg urea solution (1%)/ha, at the differentiation stage of primordial panicle.

grains better. 3) The amount of nitrogen applied is not excessive. Too much nitrogen leads to excessive vegetative growth, droopy leaves, lodging, increased disease and insect damage, and reduced availability of carbohydrates for grain-filling.

The number of secondary branches and spikelets increased by 11.5-19.0% when nitrogen was applied at the primordial panicle stage. Thus proper nitrogen application may increase the number of filled grains per panicle. It

increased dry panicle weight by 13.0-18.0%.

Use of nitrogen increased the respiratory intensity of primordial panicles by 0.004-0.040 mg CG /g panicle per hour, perhaps because treated plants grow stronger than untreated plants.

The total nitrogen content in the leaf blade was increased by 0.27-1.0% with nitrogen application. That increased photosynthetic activity and photosynthetic products, resulting in more normal branches and spikelets and thus

higher grain yield.

The contents of starch and sugars accumulated in the leaf sheath and stem of the treated plant were higher (about 14.1% and 17.4%, respectively) than in the control plants. Such assimilated carbohydrates contribute to the primordial panicle and thus increase grain yields.

Experiments using ^{14}C and ^{32}P show that the assimilation of ^{14}C and ^{32}P distributed among the middle and the lower parts of the developed panicle spikelets increased yields (Table 2). ■

Increased productivity in rice through inhibition of photorespiration

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Rice, a photorespiring plant (C3-type), loses much of its yield through photorespiration. Treatments with some inhibitors of photorespiration may increase the yield of this crop. In an experiment to test this hypothesis, neutralized aqueous solutions (10^{-3}M) of three photorespiratory inhibitors — isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH), sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3), and L-glutamic acid — were foliarly sprayed on the rice variety NC1281 at preflowering and postflowering stages and yield parameters were recorded. The yield parameters included fertility percentage, sterility percentage, grain weight per plant, thousand-grain weight, and grain-straw ratio.

Photorespiratory inhibitors applied at either the preflowering or postflowering stage markedly improved yield parameters and yield per plant (see table). The postflowering treatments showed better effects on yield parameters than the pre-

Effects of photorespiratory inhibitors on some yield parameters and yield of rice (NC1281), West Bengal, India.

Treatment (10^{-3}M)	Ripened grains (%)	Sterile grains (%)	Grain wt ^a (g/plant)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain-straw ratio
<i>Preflowering stage (145 days after sowing)</i>					
Control	86.27	13.73	16.20	26.49	0.345
INH	86.54	13.46	20.50 (+ 26.5)	26.52	0.357
NaHCO_3	87.22	12.78	17.30 (+ 6.8)	26.53	0.389
L-glutamic acid	85.38	14.62	16.00 (- 1.2)	26.45	0.340
<i>Postflowering stage (157 days after sowing)</i>					
INH	88.29	11.71	22.10 (+ 36.4)	26.55	0.452
NaHCO_3	87.32	12.68	21.00 (+ 29.6)	26.45	0.378
L-glutamic acid	86.43	13.57	20.00 (+ 23.4)	26.44	0.299

^aFigures within parentheses indicate percentage increases (+) or decreases (-) in yield in relation to the control.

flowering treatments and increased yield per plant considerably over the control. Among the inhibitors used, INH (inhibitor of glycolate pathway) was the most effective; it was followed by NaHCO_3 (inhibitor of RuBP carboxylase-oxygenase). L-glutamic acid (inhibitor of glycolate pathway), when applied at preflowering stage, slightly inhibited yield, but when applied at postflowering stage, significantly increased yield and other

yield parameters. The increase in yield could be ascribed to increased ripened grains and lower sterility. Thousand-grain weight of treated plants did not, however, vary distinctly from the control. The grain-straw ratio was positively correlated with grain weight per plant. Thus, some suitable photorespiratory inhibitors applied at a particular developmental stage of the plant could increase rice yield significantly. ■

A simple method for studying temperature and relative humidity within the rice plant canopy

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The conventional hygrothermograph measures the temperature-humidity levels in a given field, but not the actual microclimate between the tillers and areas where propagules of disease or insect pest organisms begin to develop. Equipment to measure such *microenvironmental* climates exists, but is difficult

to procure and unsafe in most Asian fields.

We have tested a simple system to measure the atmospheric moisture and temperature between tillers of rice clumps with several replications. A weighing bottle with 1 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 (AR) is weighed with its